

UNDERSTANDING THE CULTURAL TRADITIONS OF THE UZBEKISTAN PEOPLE AMONG PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ANNOTATION

Educating preschool children on the basis of national values is one of the important pedagogical tasks. The rich cultural heritage, customs, traditions of the Uzbek people are of great importance in forming in children an understanding of national identity, feelings of patriotism, respect and kindness. Since children at this age quickly perceive the environment, it is appropriate to explain folk customs to them in a simple and interesting way.

Key words: value, international, people, national centers, historical roots, universal.

METHODOLOGY

Today, the comprehensive and spiritually mature upbringing of the younger generation is one of the priority areas of state policy. Especially in preschool children, it is important to form a sense of respect for national values, knowledge and appreciation of the traditions of their people. Because it is during this period that the child's personality, worldview and social behavior begin to form. The concept of cultural customs of the Uzbek people. Customs are the way of life, customs, rituals and traditions of the people that have been formed over the centuries. The customs of the Uzbek people are distinguished by the following: respect for elders, hospitality, loyalty to family and kinship ties, hard work, kindness and generosity. The concept of customs of the Uzbek people. Customs are traditions and rituals that have been formed during the historical development of the people and are passed down from generation to generation. The traditions of the Uzbek people embody the spiritual life, moral standards and social relations of the people. Preschool age is one of the most important periods in the formation of a child as a person. It is during this period that the child's worldview, moral qualities, social behavior and attitude to national identity begin to form. Therefore, teaching preschool children the traditions of the Uzbek people is of great pedagogical importance. First of all, traditions develop a sense of national identity in children. As a child gets acquainted with the traditions, rituals and values of his people, he begins to feel himself as a part of this nation. This in turn will form the basis for the formation of a sense of patriotism, national pride and devotion to his culture in the future. Traditions serve to form

moral education in children. Qualities such as respect for elders, kindness to younger ones, hospitality, generosity, and etiquette are instilled in children through folk customs in a simple and understandable way. For example, greeting etiquette, giving place to elders, and the culture of behavior around the table develop positive behavior in children. Teaching customs accelerates the process of socialization of children. A child learns to behave as a member of society, understands the rules of living in a community, and mutual relationships. By participating in holidays, ceremonies, and national games, children learn to communicate and work together. National customs develop children's speech and thinking. Through fairy tales, proverbs, songs, and national games, children's vocabulary expands and their thinking skills develop. At the same time, elements of national culture form a child's aesthetic taste. Also, teaching customs develops children's mental stability and positive emotions. Holidays and traditional ceremonies bring joy to children and help them feel free in the national environment.

DISCUSSION

The importance of teaching customs to preschool children. Teaching customs at preschool age: forms national pride in children, develops moral qualities, enriches speech and thinking, and sets social behavior on the right path. The main customs that are explained to children. Greeting etiquette, children are taught to greet adults, say "Assalamu alaykum", and treat them with respect. This custom is the basis of upbringing and manners. Hospitality, the hospitality inherent in the Uzbek people, is explained to children through fairy tales and stage performances. Welcoming guests with honor, treating guests well are brought up. Respect for adults, respecting parents, grandparents, teachers, and helping them are instilled in children's daily lives. National holidays and ceremonies, children are given simple concepts about holidays such as Navruz, Ramadan, and Kurban. During holidays, culture is introduced through national clothes, national dishes, and games. National clothes, such as atlas, adras, skullcaps, and jackets, arouse interest in national culture in children. Methods of teaching traditions, the following methods are used in teaching traditions in preschool educational organizations: fairy tales and stories, national games, stage performances, pictures and visual aids, songs and poems. The role of the educator, in teaching traditions to children, the educator must: be an example, respect national values, and take into account the age characteristics of children.

RESULT

As a result of systematic and purposeful teaching of the traditions of the Uzbek people to preschool children, a number of positive changes are observed in children.

First of all, children develop interest and respect for national values. They gain initial understanding of the traditions, holidays and ceremonies of their people. In the process of teaching traditions, children's moral education is strengthened. Such qualities as respect for adults, kindness to peers, and adherence to etiquette begin to manifest themselves in children's daily behavior. This improves their relationships in the community. Also, classes organized on the basis of national traditions develop children's speech, thinking, and creative abilities. Through fairy tales, songs, and national games, children's vocabulary expands and independent thinking skills are formed.

As a result, the level of social adaptation in preschool children increases, they learn to behave in a team, communicate, and work cooperatively. Most importantly, children develop a sense of national identity, patriotism, and the foundations of spiritual maturity.

CONCLUSION

Forming an understanding of the cultural traditions of the Uzbek people in preschool children is an important factor in their growth as a well-rounded individual. A child brought up on the basis of national values will grow up to be a person loyal to his people and homeland in the future. Teaching traditions to preschool children serves their comprehensive development and creates a solid foundation for them to grow up as well-rounded, cultured individuals in the future. National tolerance is not ensured at the expense of harming the national interest, which is contrary to this. It is strengthened on the basis of considering and ensuring the interests of different nations. When determining the importance of a particular value, one should not forget that there are such systems, and one should not lose sight of its position for a particular era, social unit, sphere, process, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Shavkat Mirziyoyev. "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people". Tashkent Uzbekistan 2017.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". – Tashkent.
3. Concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent.
4. Avloniy A. Turkiy guliston or morality. – Tashkent: Teacher.
5. Rasulov X. National values and education. – Tashkent: Ma'naviyat.
6. A. Kholmatova. Forming a sense of respect for cultural values in preschool children. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ISSN 2195-1381 Volume- 5 June 2025 <http://ijarer.org/index.php/ij/index>

7. A. Kholmatova. Methodology for forming a sense of respect for cultural values in preschool education. MINISTRY OF PRE-SCHOOL AND SCHOOL EDUCATION